

Artificial Data Directory list

August 2024

A1 - Root directory for first artificial dataset(**RQ1**).

RIW - Directory for retrospective data.

RESULTS_PER_DAY - Test history split by number of days.

ANALYSIS - Test analysis results for grid searches across H and λ value.

SCORES - Flakiness scores by history length.

DAY_1 - Flakiness scores for 1 day of data by λ value.

DAY_2 - Flakiness scores for 2 days of data by λ value.

DAY_4 - Flakiness scores for 4 days of data by λ value.

DAY_8 - Flakiness scores for 8 days of data by λ value.

DAY_16 - Flakiness scores for 16 days of data by λ value.

DAY_32 - Flakiness scores for 32 days of data by λ value.

DAY_64 - Flakiness scores for 64 days of data by λ value.

ANALYSIS - Test analysis results for grid searches across perspectives.

GROUND_TRUTHS - Ground truth datasets, including run schedules and version samples data.

RESULTS - Generated test history not split.

PIW - Directory for prospective data - same directory structure as RIW

PLOTS

ANALYSIS - Plots generated during analysis.

RIW - Plots for scores based on the retrospective dataset.

UA_UNWEIGHTED_SCORE - Plots based on the unweighted scores showing the comparison of parameters.

UA_WEIGHTED_SCORE.1 - Plots based on the weighted scores showing the comparison of parameters.

PIW - Plots for scores based on the retrospective dataset - same directory structure as RIW.

GROUND_TRUTHS - Plots based on ground truth, showing (a) Trend of original P_flake values, (b) Verdict progression for test samples as a heatmap.

A2 - Root directory for second artificial dataset(**RQ2**). Has the same directory structure as the first artificial dataset. The analysis directory also includes plots of the comparisons of the trend of the original P_flake values and the flakiness scores for each version formulae, history length and λ value showing the Fréchet distance within the plot for each test.

